

FEATURES OF SPORTS SELECTION OF GIRLS FOR INITIAL TRAINING GROUPS IN GYMNASTICS

Khankeldiev Sher Khakimovich

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Khudieva Sabina

master's degree

Fergana State University

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ABSTRACT

The problem of developing the motor abilities of gymnasts over the years not only does not lose its relevance, but also raises new questions that need to be solved using modern scientific methods, in accordance with the trends and prospects for the development of world gymnastics.

Relevance. In general, the problem of developing motor abilities is taken quite seriously: in Uzbekistan and abroad, numerous studies are being conducted in which new, previously unknown human reserve capabilities are being discovered, and more modern methods of developing physical abilities are being developed. However, they often rush to introduce a new method into practice without proper testing, extend the method of training adults to train young gymnasts, forget about the colossal experience of their gymnastics school and grab onto any foreign innovation. But on the other hand, understanding the importance of developing motor qualities, we ourselves try to solve many pressing issues without, as a rule, being well-versed in the whole problem, and therefore we do not achieve success in solving particular problems. Thus, already far-fetched problematic issues arise, difficulties are aggravated, and sometimes disbelief in one's own and students' capabilities arises, the conviction that "science is a bad helper" comes, and dissatisfaction develops with all the ensuing consequences.

For children of primary school age, the need for high physical activity is natural. It is laid down by the hereditary program of the individual development of the child and determines the need for constant reinforcement of the expanding functional capabilities of the organs and structures of the child's body. If these organs and structures do not show constant activity, then their development processes are inhibited and, as a consequence, various functional and morphological disorders arise. At the same time, constant activity is a kind of "trigger mechanism" for the progressive increase in the functional capabilities of children.

Motor activity is understood as the total number of motor actions performed by a person in the process of everyday life. There are regulated, partially regulated and non-regulated motor activity. Regulated physical activity is the total volume of specially selected and directed motor actions affecting the body of schoolchildren (for example, in a physical education lesson). Partially regulated motor activity is the volume of motor actions that arise in the course of solving motor problems (for example, during a hiking trip).

Unregulated motor activity includes the volume of spontaneously performed motor actions (for example, in everyday life). The average rate of physical activity, including all its varieties, for primary schoolchildren should be at least 12-18 thousand movements per day with the obligatory inclusion of 1-1.5 hours of organized physical education classes.

The amount of time for regulated physical activity of primary schoolchildren includes physical education lessons (twice a week for 45 minutes), physical education minutes (5 minutes), active breaks (20-30 minutes), a sports hour in an extended day group (50-60 minutes) and completing homework on: physical education (15-25 min). This volume can be increased through extracurricular sports activities (clubs, sports sections, competitions, etc.).

When considering the issues of physical activity of children of primary school age, it is necessary to take into account the nature of their daily activities related to schooling. Particular attention should be paid to 1st grade students. For a child, the beginning of education is a critical period when he turns from "playing" to "sitting". Evidence of this is the decrease in motor activity in first-graders by an average of 50% compared to preschoolers. At primary school age, there are significant differences in physical activity parameters between boys and girls: boys have these indicators on average 16-30% higher.

Medical and biological characteristics. Children of primary school age are sensitive to targeted effects on the development of their motor function and improvement of the morphological structures of the motor system. At this age, a uniform increase in body length and an increase in its weight are observed. Thanks to the development of muscles and ligaments, the cervical and thoracic curvature of the spine is formed, which is characteristic of correct posture. At the same time, the relatively weak development of muscles that ensure long-term maintenance of static tension when holding various body poses, as well as significant elasticity of the ligaments, can cause deformation of the musculoskeletal system, the occurrence of scoliosis and flat feet. The average indicators of physical development of children of primary school age are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Average physical development indicators for girls primary school age

Indicators	Age, years		
		7	7-8
Height, cm	d	120	127
Body weight, kg	d	21.9	25.2
Vital capacity of the lungs - vital capacity. l	d	1.33	1.46
Chest circumference, cm	d	57.2	61.0
Dynamometry of the right hand, kg	d	5.1	7.4

At primary school age (compared to the previous preschool age), there is a significant acceleration in the rate of structural transformations in all parts of the cardiovascular system: the mass of the heart increases, thickening of the myocardial walls is observed, a wide lumen of blood vessels and a relatively larger minute volume of blood than in adults (in per kilogram of body weight) provide sufficient blood supply to organs. However, unlike adults, the required minute volume is achieved in these children mainly due to the heart rate (HR), which compensates for the relatively small stroke volume of the heart (the amount of blood ejected by the heart in one contraction). A high heart rate against the background of low blood pressure causes additional stress on the cardiovascular system. Systolic blood pressure in schoolchildren averages 95-110 mmHg. Art., and diastolic - $2/3$ of it. With age, stroke volume increases and heart rate decreases, which indicates an increase in the reserve capacity of the heart.

In the period from 6-7 to 9-10 years, the weight of the lungs increases significantly, the number of alveoli approaches their number in adults. Structural changes in the lungs cause an increase in their vital capacity (the maximum volume of air in one respiratory cycle).

Thus, the vital capacity of the lungs (VC) increases from 1.40 - 1.60 to 2.20 - 2.50 liters. Simultaneously with the increase in the capabilities of external respiration and the cardiovascular system, there is an increase in oxygen consumption, both under conditions of rest and during strenuous physical work. These changes reflect an increase in the ability to supply muscles with oxygen and an improvement in energy exchange processes. Positive changes in the respiratory system characterize the expansion of its functional boundaries, but it is still far from perfect. This primarily affects the time it takes to perform physical activity, when younger schoolchildren have a high respiratory rate and relatively small tidal volumes, ineffective utilization of oxygen from ventilated air, and a high energy cost of mechanical work (the amount of energy spent on 1 kgm of work).

An important feature of children of primary school age is the dynamics of the development of analyzers. Thus, the areas of the cerebral cortex related to the motor analyzer are already becoming quite mature. At the same time, there are still no close functional relationships between the motor, visual and other analyzers. At this age, there is also insufficient maturity of the areas of the cerebral cortex that program and control voluntary movements, which is reflected in both the development and reproduction of many movements with a complex motor structure.

Thus, the functional capabilities of younger schoolchildren are inferior in many respects to the capabilities of adults, but the progressive development of individual organs and structures makes it possible to purposefully influence their more accelerated development and thereby increase the functional capabilities of the body as a whole. For the practice of physical education, indicators of the functional capabilities of the child's body are the leading criteria when choosing physical activity, the structure of motor actions, and methods of influencing the body.

Psychological and pedagogical characteristics. Primary school age is the most favorable for the development of many physical abilities, as evidenced by the average functional indicators of children of primary school age at rest and at maximum load (Table 2).

table 2

Indicators	Age, years				
		6-7		7-8	
		peace	Job	peace	Job
Heart rate , beats/min	d	95.4	192.3	87.2	187.3
Impact blood emission , ml	d	25.2	40.4	32.3	42.9
frequency . cycle/min	d	24.2	69.4	23.3	51.4
Tidal volume, ml/cycle	d	190	344	186	360
Oxygen consumption , ml/min kg	d	6.2	35.4	6.4	27.8

Average functional indicators of girls of primary school age at rest and at maximum load

Among the physical abilities that develop most intensively in primary school age are speed and coordination abilities (simple coordination), as well as the ability to perform cyclic actions for a long time in modes of moderate and high intensity. Within the framework of the pedagogical process, the development of physical abilities is carried out in two main directions: the first is stimulating the development of physical abilities and the second is directed development. Stimulating development is carried out in the process of forming motor skills. It is associated with teaching children the basics of motor control, which contributes to the development of physical abilities, primarily coordination.

Directed development is manifested in increasing the functional capabilities of certain organs and structures of the body (external respiration, blood circulation, energy supply, etc.), improving their interaction during the performance of motor actions. Increased functionality is ensured by performing well-mastered exercises. With a change in load size.

When conducting physical exercises, schoolchildren try to imitate the teacher, copy his actions in the process of performing motor tasks. At the same time, the motivational basis for performing motor actions is the desire to keep up with one's peers, to receive encouragement from a teacher or friends. Younger schoolchildren are characterized by a relatively rapid change in emotional activity and a transition to a passive state. There are at least two reasons behind this phenomenon. The first is due to the fact that high emotional stress, which affects the child for a long time, leads to the development of inhibition processes in the central zones of the higher parts of the nervous system (protective reflex), and the second is due to the low level of general physical performance, which determines the very rapid development of fatigue of the body as a whole. . At the same time, younger schoolchildren quickly recover from exercise, and they again have a need for physical activity. This change in functional activity in the behavior of schoolchildren predetermines the need to choose the optimal alternation of load and rest. It is necessary to avoid prolonged, monotonous performance of monotonous motor actions, as well as prolonged emotional stress. The educational process must constantly include new tasks, motor actions, and various forms of organizing classes, - allowing each student to demonstrate their physical potential to the fullest extent.

Proper selection of children into sports schools is one of the most important conditions for the successful preparation of young athletes. The basis for the development of sports selection methods is the doctrine of sports abilities.

During selection, children are identified for whom the training process in this sport gives the maximum effect. The selection is based on a deep and comprehensive study of the children's personality, health status, identification of morphological, functional and psychological characteristics, assessment of the typological properties of the nervous system, level of physical qualities, etc.

The methodology for selecting young athletes in each sport includes a complex of various methods (pedagogical, psychological, medical-biological, etc.), with the help of which it was possible to sufficiently fully identify and evaluate those qualities of children on which the success of each of them depends on their chosen kind of sport. A particular difficulty lies in the fact that it is necessary to evaluate not only the existing properties, but also to predict how they will develop during training.

Let's consider the main criteria for selecting girls for artistic gymnastics. The age of children should not exceed 6-8 years.

Anthropometric criteria are given in table. 1.

The critical importance for gymnasts of relative strength, mobility in joints, and coordination capabilities is determined by the control standards for physical fitness used during the initial selection (Table 4).

During the medical examination of girls selected for gymnastics, special attention should be paid to the condition of the musculoskeletal and vestibular system. It is also important to evaluate the psychological qualities of children - courage when performing unfamiliar exercises, perseverance when practicing movements for a long time. Of exceptional importance is the assessment of the ability to quickly master new movements, the expressiveness of motor activity, which subsequently determines the composition, rhythm and pattern of movements, plasticity and dynamism, grace and elegance of execution.

Assessment of the main indicators of the physical development of children (girls) during selection for artistic gymnastics (Platonov V.N.)

Table 4

Age, years	Physical development indicator	Level		
		Below the average	Average	Above average
7	Body length, cm	106 - 108	110 - 112	114 - 120
	Mass, kg	14 - 16.5	16 - 18	18 - 20
	Chest circumference, cm	49.0 - 51.5	52.0 - 54.5	55.0 - 59.0
8	Body length, cm	113 - 115	116 - 118	119 - 122
	Mass, kg	15.5 - 17	18 - 20.5	21 - 24
	Chest circumference, cm	52.0 - 54.5	55.5 - 57.5	58.5 - 60.5
9	Body length, cm	117 - 119	120 - 124	124 - 130
	Mass, kg	18 - 20	20 - 22	23 - 28
	Chest circumference, cm	55.0 - 57.0	57.5 - 60	62.0 - 63.5

Control standards for physical fitness used in the initial selection of gymnasts (girls) (Platonov V.N.)

Control test	Age, years	Index
1. Running 20 m on the move, s	7	4.3
	8	4.2
2. Standing long jump, cm	7	140
	8	150
3. Hanging pull-ups, quantity	7	5
	8	8
4. Hanging angle, s	7	18
	8	26
5. Forward tilt, cm	7	8.1
	8	8.6
6. Bridge from a prone position, point	7	8.1
	8	8.6

Summarizing the results of the study of literary sources revealing the development of motor abilities in groups of initial training, it can be noted that their development at the age of 7-10 years is the most important component in the preparation of reserves, as well as the further increase in the sports achievements of young gymnasts.

The need to solve a large number of problems with the help of physical training puts forward the condition for a clear correlation between the content of different types and sections of work carried out at the stages and during periods of training and improvement of gymnasts. At the same time, the organization of physical training at different stages has a number of significant features both in terms of tasks and content. Solving initial training problems is mandatory for all training groups of gymnasts, regardless of age. And this is due to their readiness for specialized improvement, development at the proper level of qualities, abilities and some skills. At the same time, the authors' opinions on the content, methodology and means of developing motor abilities in initial training groups are not clear.

Taking into account these discrepancies, we believe that this differentiation of physical training into general and special at the stage of initial training is conditional.

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